

PVC-based heterogeneous chelating inorganic exchanger membrane as sensors for the determination of zinc(II) ions

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Abstract : A PVC membrane electrode for Zn^{II} ion based on heterogeneous chelating inorganic ion exchange resin i.e. tetracycline hydrochloride sorbed tin(IV) tungstophosphate is reported. The electrode works well over a wide range of concentration (1.5×10^{-5} to $1 \times 10^{-1} M$) with a Nernstian slope of 27.3 mV per decade of concentrations. The electrode shows a fast response time of 25 s and operates in the pH range 4–6. The sensor can be used for more than three months without any divergence in the potential. The selectivity of the electrode was studied and was found that the electrode exhibits good selectivity for zinc ions over a wide variety of cations including alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. The zinc ion selectivity electrode was used as an indicator electrode for the potentiometric titration of zinc ions in solution against standard EDTA solution. The applicability of the sensor to zinc(II) ion measurements in high tensile brass is also illustrated.

Keywords : Ion-exchangers, sensors, zinc(II) ions, PVC-based membranes.

The chelating ion exchangers have been developed recently and their analytical applications explored^{1,2}. A number of such ion exchangers have been prepared by the incorporation of ligands on resins³⁻⁵. The chelating ion exchange resins are found to possess specific selectivity for some metal ions and play an important role in separation processes. For example, 2-hydroxy acetophenoneoxime-thiourea trioxane resin membrane for uranyl ions⁶, resacetophenoneoxime condensed with formaldehyde forms a resin for copper ions⁷ and a number of compounds having 2-hydroxyacryloximes⁸ have been impregnated in polymeric matrices and found extensive applications in the hydrometallurgy of copper ions. Similarly, the utilities of salicylaldehyde-formaldehyde resin membrane for the estimation of zinc⁹ and 1-hydroxy-2-naphthaldoxime-formaldehyde resin membrane for the nickel ions¹⁰ have also been reported in the literature.

The present paper deals with the electroanalytical applicability of tetracycline hydrochloride sorbed tin(IV) tungstophosphate (TC-TWP) resin membrane as a zinc ion sensor. The proposed sensor has excellent selectivity for zinc ions over the other cations. Studies of complexation between metals and ion exchangers¹¹ have yielded valuable information for the construction and design of sensors. Tetracycline hydrochloride (shown below) a broad-spectrum antibiotic, is large cyclic organic molecule containing O and N, capable of forming electron rich interior cavities and

possessing the ability to complex through dipole-dipole or ion-dipole interactions with metal ions of compatible dimensions.

Although the resin mentioned above shows a selectivities uptake of some metal ions in the sequence¹² : $Fe^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Pb^{2+}$, the membrane selectivity does not necessarily follow the same pattern and is different from the pure material owing to the application of neutral binders, incorporated during fabrication. The presence of binding material affects the conductance of the membrane, which is an additional parameter of the sensor affecting the selectivity in comparison with the electroactive phase taken in the pure state¹³.

Results and discussion

Tetracycline hydrochloride sorbed tin(IV) tungstophosphate (TC-TWP) belongs to the class of mixed heteropoly acids. Literature data have demonstrated that it is possible to exchange metal ions reversibly with a cation present in solution, once the electrode is dipped in a specific electrolyte, whose characteristics constitute the driving force for ion discrimination : the size and shape of the ion are the

limiting factors inserted into the structure. This behaviour, which is typical for some inorganic materials having three-dimensional structures with interstitial sites depending on the particular geometric domains, has been ascribed as the mechanisms of the response process often displayed by ion selective electrodes (ISEs) based on inorganic 'sensing' materials. Another proposed mechanism of the potentiometric response is selective adsorption of the primary ion on the electrode surface. It is generally found to be correlated with the solubility product of an insoluble salt of the primary ion, such as in the case of silver halides and metal sulfides¹⁴.

Table 1. Response time for non-aqueous solvents (Zn²⁺-selective membrane electrode)

Sl. no.	Time (h)	Potential (mV)			
		10% ethanol	5% ethanol	10% acetone	5% acetone
1.	0	39	33	34	31
2.	5	35	29	34	32
3.	10	34	27	30	31
4.	15	31	24	29	30
5.	20	29	22	28	29
6.	25	26	18	25	26
7.	30	21	15	23	24
8.	35	15	12	20	21
9.	40	14	10	19	20
10.	45	13	9	16	16
11.	50	13	9	16	14
12.	55	13	9	16	11
13.	60	13	9	16	11
14.	65	13	9	16	11

The potential response of the membrane obtained with pure solutions is illustrated in Fig. 1. It is observed that the membrane electrode can measure Zn²⁺ ions in the range 1.5×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-1} M as per IUPAC recommendations and it also exhibits Nernstian behaviour (slope 27.3 mV per decade of concentration). The pH dependence of the membrane sensor has been tested at the concentration 1.0×10^{-2} M of Zn²⁺ ions. The working pH range of the sensor is only 4.0–6.0 (Fig. 2). A sharp change in potentials beyond this range (< 4 and > 6) may be due to competitive influence of H⁺ ions.

The static response time of the sensor was found to be ~25 s over the entire concentration range. This is actually the average time required for the electrode to reach a potential within ± 1 mV of the equilibrium value after successive immersion of a series of Zn²⁺ ions, each having a ten-fold differences in concentration and the potentials remains constant for more than 3 min, after which a very slow divergence is observed. Under laboratory conditions, if the membrane is properly stored in distilled water and if cross-contamination is avoided, it can be used for period of over three months without observing any drift in potential. Thereafter it can be regenerated or else a new membrane can be fabricated and used. However, it is necessary to keep the membrane dipped in 0.1 M Zn²⁺ solutions when not in working condition to standardized the membrane and activate the electroactive material present in the membrane.

The performance of the proposed sensor system was also investigated in partially non-aqueous media using water-ethanol and water-acetone mixtures. The membrane works well in a partially non-aqueous medium up to a maximum of 10% (v/v) non-aqueous content without any change in the Nernstian slope (mV/decade conc. change). However, at larger non-aqueous contents (>10%) the slope and working concentration range decrease appreciably. In addition to this, the response time of the membrane electrode has also been investigated in non-aqueous systems and observed that the response times are steady for few hours to days, after that the potential deviates significantly (Table 1).

The rate and the efficiency of the selective insertion/release reaction involving TC-TWP and counter cations can be checked by the potentiometric selectivity coefficients. The order of the selectivities obtained may be due to the effective hydrated diameter of the cations¹⁵, which may reflect the size as a whole of the intercalated ions, allowing selective ion insertion/release. The lack of any kind of selectivity order concerning monovalent species is possibly due to a different mechanism of the potentiometric response. In this case the selectivity towards A⁺ ions may reflect the binding (adsorption) affinity of the ions, similar to the responses of electrodes based on conventional insoluble salts¹⁴.

Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij}^{Pot}) were determined with the

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij}) values of Zn²⁺-selective based on (TC-TWP)-PVC membrane electrode for different cations

M ²⁺ , (3+for Cr, Al, Fe)	Mg	Ca	Sr	Ba	Cd	Mn	Cu	Hg	Ni	Co	Cr	Al	Fe
Selectivity coefficients $\times 10^2$	16.7	16.7	8.18	4.55	8.18	5.56	4.55	3.33	8.18	8.16	0.37	0.18	0.37

Fig. 1. Calibration curve of Zn^{2+} -selective (TC-TWP)-PVC based membrane electrode.

method of mixed solutions for Zn^{2+} ion selective electrode by varying zinc ion concentrations and keeping the fixed concentration of interfering ions at $1 \times 10^{-2} M$. K_{ij}^{Pot} was calculated from the equation :

$$K_{ij}^{Pot} = \frac{a_i}{(a_j)^{z_i/z_j}} (10^{(E_2 - E_1)\theta} - 1) \quad (1)$$

where a_i and a_j are the activities of the main and foreign ions; z_i and z_j are the charges of the main and foreign ions; E_1 and E_2 are the potentials of ISE in the background and mixed solutions; θ is the slope of the electrode function. The results are shown in Table 2, which indicates that they would not significantly disturb the functioning of the Zn^{2+} -selective membrane.

The proposed membrane electrode was found to work well under laboratory conditions. The electrode was used as an indicator in successful titration of a zinc ion solution with EDTA ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$). The result is shown in Fig. 2, indicating that the amount of zinc can be accurately determined with the electrode.

The proposed Zn^{II} electrode was also successfully used for the direct potentiometric determination of zinc in high tensile brass. The results were compared with data obtained by cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). The results clearly indicate that the content of Zn^{II} in the high tensile brass as measured by Zn^{II} sensor are in good agreement with those obtained by cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometric method.

Experimental

Chemicals :

All chemicals and reagents for the preparation of membranes and metal salts (chlorides) were of analytical reagent grade (C.D.H., India). High molecular weight poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) (degree of polymerization, 1020 from Fluka, Switzerland) and tetracycline hydrochloride

(C.D.H., India) were used without further treatment. Metal solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardized by appropriate methods.

Fig. 2. pH vs electrode potential for Zn^{2+} -selective (TC-TWP)-PVC based membrane electrode.

Synthesis of chelating inorganic ion exchange resin :

The exchanger, tin(IV) tungstophosphate was prepared as reported method¹⁶ by adding 0.1 M tin(IV) chloride solution to 0.1 M tungstophosphoric acid solution in a ratio of 2 : 1 at a desired pH value. The resulting precipitate was allowed to stand for 24 h at room temperature. It was filtered and washed with 1 M HCl followed by deionized water (DIW). The gel was dried at $40 \pm 2^\circ C$. The dried product was broken down into small granules by immersing it in water. These granules were dried and were subjected to refluxing in 6 M H_3PO_4 for 100 h. The resulting material was washed with DIW and then converted into H^+ form by treatment with 1 M HNO_3 in usual manner. Finally the sorption of tetracycline hydrochloride on tin(IV) tungstophosphate was done according to the procedure previously described⁵.

Preparation of membrane :

The membrane was prepared by adding diluent tetrahydrofuran (6 mL) containing PVC (0.6 g) to an electroactive material (TC-TWP) (0.2 g). The resulting solution

was carefully cast on a glass slide plate and left for slow evaporation to obtain a thin membrane¹⁷ Then an appropriate size of membrane was cut from the master membrane and was mounted at the lower end of the membrane holder with araldite

Potential measurements

The membrane was equilibrated with 0.1 M Zn(NO₃)₂ solution for 3–4 days and the potential generated across the membrane was measured by setting up the following electrochemical cell assembly

Internal reference electrode	Internal 0.1 M Zn ²⁺ solution	Membrane	Test solutions	Internal reference electrode
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Saturated calomel electrodes (SCE) were employed as reference electrodes and all potential measurements were made by using an Equiptronic-India Digital Potentiometer [EQ 602] at 25 ± 1 °C. Before each set of measurements, electrodes were conditioned overnight in an appropriate buffer solution containing 0.1 M Zn(NO₃)₂ solution.

Determination of zinc in high tensile brass :

0.1, 0.2, 0.3 and 0.5 g of high tensile brass were weighed accurately and the samples were treated with aqua regia separately. The sample solution was evaporated to dryness and finally the residue was taken up in water. The tin present in the sample was precipitated as hydrous stannic oxide. The filtrate was treated with H₂SO₄ and evaporated to fumes to expel nitric acid and the residual liquid was taken up with distilled water. Undissolved lead sulphate was filtered off and the copper was precipitated as copper-thiocyanate by treating the solution with ammonium thiocyanate solution. Heat the solution nearly to boiling and then add concentration NH₄OH until a permanent precipi-

tate was obtained, which was again filtered. The filtrate was boiled and evaporated to minimal amount. Finally the residual liquid was cooled and taken up with double distilled water and made up to the volume of 100 mL.

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